

Retrospective BLAST Analysis Detects RaTG13/Ra4991 in the Earliest SARS-CoV-2 Genome Submitted to NCBI GenBank (December 28, 2019)

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Abstract:

On December 28, 2019, Dr. Lili Ren submitted a near-complete genome sequence of a novel coronavirus (BetaCoV/Wuhan/IPBCAMS-WH-01/2019) to NCBI GenBank - the earliest known SARS-CoV-2 sequence sent outside China. At the time, GenBank already contained an embargoed partial RdRp sequence of RaTG13/Ra4991 (accession MH615898.1), a strain that would later be recognized as the closest known relative to SARS-CoV-2, deposited in July 2018.

This retrospective BLAST analysis demonstrates that a standard nucleotide search of Dr. Ren's December 28, 2019, sequence would have produced a strong match of 97.79% identity to the embargoed 2018 fragment. A subsequent keyword search for "Ra4991" would have rapidly linked the emerging virus to the Mojiang mine and the 2012 miner outbreak. These findings strongly suggest that a clear early warning signal would have been detectable in late December 2019 using routine bioinformatics tools and data already available in the NIH GenBank system.

While the discovery of RaTG13 as the closest known relative to SARS-CoV-2 has been widely attributed to a Chinese research team's publication in Nature on February 3, 2020

(with ~96.2% genome-wide identity), this study reveals that a significantly earlier detection opportunity existed in the United States.

A routine BLAST search performed on the near-complete SARS-CoV-2 genome submitted by Dr. Lili Ren to NCBI GenBank on December 28, 2019, would have produced a strong partial match of 97.79% identity to a partial RdRp sequence of the same virus (Ra4991/RaTG13), which had been deposited in GenBank in July 2018 under embargo.

Notably, this early detection opportunity would not have depended on any additional data transparency from China, as both sequences were already present in NCBI GenBank, the NIH-administered database in the United States. A subsequent keyword search for “Ra4991” would have quickly linked the emerging Wuhan virus to bat samples collected in the Mojiang mine, the site of a lethal SARS-like pneumonia outbreak in 2012 that killed three miners.

These findings demonstrate that a clear early warning signal was detectable in real time in late December 2019 using routine bioinformatics tools and data already present inside the NIH system.

Introduction

On December 28, 2019, Dr. Lili Ren, a virologist at the Institute of Pathogen Biology in Beijing, submitted a near-complete genome sequence of a novel coronavirus originating from Wuhan to NIH GenBank, the public genetic sequence database operated by the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI). This sequence (WH-01/2019) represents the earliest known SARS-CoV-2 genome sent outside China. At the exact time of submission, GenBank already held an embargoed partial sequence of RaTG13/Ra4991 (MH615898.1), deposited in July 2018.¹

This paper examines whether a routine BLAST search performed on Ren’s December 28, 2019, sequence — for a user who had access to the embargoed data inside the NCBI database — would have revealed a significant match to the 2018 Ra4991 fragment and, by extension, to the Mojiang mine and the 2012 miner outbreak. Such access could have at the time been available to NCBI/GenBank database administrators, other qualified NIH personnel, and, presumably, authorized analysts within U.S. biodefense and intelligence agencies tasked with early warning and pathogen surveillance.

¹ Notably: the embargoed 2018 partial RdRp sequence also lists Edward Holmes among the associated authors. Holmes later co-authored several high-profile papers on SARS-CoV-2 origins, including “The Proximal Origin of SARS-CoV-2” (Nature Medicine, March 17, 2020) and influential origin articles published in Science and Cell.

It further assesses the broader implications of this missed detection opportunity. The study first reviews the background of the Ren submission and the Ra4991/RaTG13 sequences. It then describes the BLAST methodology and results. Finally, the implications for early warning systems and pandemic data forensics are discussed.

Background

Documents released by the U.S. House Committee on Energy and Commerce in January 2024 revealed that Dr. Lili Ren submitted a near-complete genome sequence of a novel coronavirus on December 28, 2019 (House Committee on Energy and Commerce, 2024). At the time of this submission, GenBank already contained an embargoed partial RdRp sequence of RaTG13/Ra4991 (accession MH615898.1), deposited in July 2018. RaTG13 is the closest known relative to SARS-CoV-2, sharing approximately 96.2% genome-wide identity.

This virus was originally sampled from an abandoned mine shaft in Mojiang County, Yunnan Province — the site of a fatal SARS-like pneumonia outbreak in 2012 that killed three of six miners. The connection between RaTG13 and the Mojiang mine was only later independently uncovered by researchers Monali Rahalkar and Rossana Segreto in the spring and summer of 2020 (Ge et al., 2013; Rahalkar & Bahulikar, 2020).

Materials and Methods

The query sequence used in this analysis was the exact near-complete genome submitted by Dr. Lili Ren on December 28, 2019 (BetaCoV/Wuhan/IPBCAMS-WH-01/2019). This sequence was obtained from documents released by the U.S. House Committee on Energy and Commerce on January 17, 2024.²

A standard nucleotide BLAST search was performed using the NCBI web interface. To simulate the 2019 database state while producing clean results in 2026, the following Entrez Query filter was applied:

```
MH615898[Accession] OR ("2010/12/31":"2019/12/31"[PDAT])
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² A cleaned FASTA version of the original submission, extracted directly from the House Energy & Commerce Committee documents, was prepared and made publicly available by virologist Jesse Bloom. Direct link: https://raw.githubusercontent.com/jbloom/SARS2_28Dec2019_Genbank_submission/main/results/SARS-CoV-2_28Dec2019_submission.fasta

The filter does not alter the BLAST alignment or percent identity of any individual hit. It includes the then-embargoed 2018 Ra4991 partial sequence (MH615898.1) while restricting the rest of the search to sequences deposited before 2020, thereby approximating what an analyst with access to both public and embargoed records in the NIH GenBank system would have seen when querying Lili Ren's sequence in late December 2019.

Results

The BLAST search produced a highly significant alignment to MH615898.1:

- Percent Identity: 97.79%
- E-value: 0.0

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Your search is limited to records include: **entrez query: MH615898[Accession] OR ("2010/12/31":"2019/12/31"[PDAT])**

Job Title: SARS-CoV-2_28Dec2019_submission
RID: ZZ6BVD5D014 Search expires on 06-03 13:11 pm Download All
Program: BLASTN Citation
Database: nt See details
Query ID: lcl|Query_5161285
Description: SARS-CoV-2_28Dec2019_submission
Molecule type: dna
Query Length: 29684
Other reports: Distance tree of results MSA viewer

Filter Results

Organism only top 20 will appear exclude
Type common name, binomial, taxid or group name
+ Add organism

Percent Identity to **E value** to **Query Coverage** to

Filter Reset

Descriptions Graphic Summary Alignments Taxonomy

Sequences producing significant alignments Download Select columns Show 100

select all 100 sequences selected GenBank Graphics Distance tree of results MSA Viewer

Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bat SARS-like coronavirus strain RaTG13_Yunnan RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp) gene, partial cds	Bat SARS-like co...	4754	4754	9%	0.0	97.79%	2757	MH615898.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bat SARS-like coronavirus isolate bat-SL-CoVZC45_complete genome	Bat SARS-like co...	15256	35039	95%	0.0	91.51%	29802	MG772933.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SARS-related bat coronavirus isolate Anlong-29 RNA-dependent RNA polymerase gene, partial cds	Bat SARS-like co...	3378	3378	9%	0.0	88.50%	2795	KF294439.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SARS-related bat coronavirus isolate Anlong-97 RNA-dependent RNA polymerase gene, partial cds	Bat SARS-like co...	3373	3373	9%	0.0	88.46%	2795	KF294440.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> BtRF-BetaCoV/HuB2013_spike glycoprotein gene, complete cds	BtRF-BetaCoV/H...	3254	4786	17%	0.0	87.81%	6621	KJ473818.1

Figure 1. Strong BLAST match between Lili Ren's December 28, 2019 SARS-CoV-2 sequence and the 2018 embargoed RaTG13/Ra4991 partial fragment (MH615898.1).

The nucleotide BLAST search produced a highly significant alignment with **97.79% identity** over 9% query coverage (E-value = 0.0) to the 2018 Ra4991 partial sequence (MH615898.1). No other sequence in the search produced nearly as high a percent identity.

This demonstrates how even the limited partial RdRp sequence available in GenBank at the time could have readily identified Ra4991/RaTG13 as the closest known relative to the emerging Wuhan virus.

Replicability

Anyone can replicate this experiment exactly as performed using the data and tools described in this paper and should obtain the same results (see Appendix A for full parameters).

Conclusions

This study provides the first evidence that a direct genomic link between SARS-CoV-2 and the 2012 Mojiang miner outbreak was detectable in late December 2019 using only sequence data and standard bioinformatics tools already present inside the NIH GenBank system. An analyst with access to the embargoed 2018 Ra4991 sequence inside NCBI GenBank could have made this connection in the early days of the Wuhan outbreak through a routine BLAST search followed by a keyword search.

Just as Zhou et al. (2020) used a short RdRp fragment to initially detect RaTG13 as the closest known relative to SARS-CoV-2, this analysis demonstrates how a highly similar match was already detectable six weeks earlier. This BLAST match, followed by a basic keyword search for the result “Ra4991”, would have connected the new virus to the 2012 Mojiang miner deaths. Instead, GenBank deleted Lili Ren’s sequence on January 16, 2020.³

Notably, the discovery path presented in this paper does not require any prior knowledge of “RaTG13” or that Ra4991 and RaTG13 are the same virus. The method described requires no post-pandemic knowledge and could have been executed using only data available in late December 2019.

That this early warning signal was missed, under circumstances that remain unclear to this day, highlights a significant gap in early outbreak detection and origin assessment. It also remains unknown whether U.S. intelligence agencies or other public health authorities conducted any follow-up analysis on the Ra4991 partial sequence. Because all necessary

³ It is notable that, at the time of submission, Ren was also a subgrantee on the NIH-funded project “Understanding the Risk of Bat Coronavirus Emergence” — the same grant that included gain-of-function experiments on bat coronaviruses at the Wuhan Institute of Virology.

data were already present in the United States and did not depend on further Chinese disclosures, these results may prompt a re-examination of the role that limited data transparency within U.S. institutions played in the initial global response.

This paper does not claim to have recreated every operational circumstance that existed inside NCBI at the time. A definitive assessment would require a much more detailed investigation into factors such as database access controls, embargo procedures, and other operational realities within the NIH GenBank system at that time. Rather, this study demonstrates a method by which a strong match to Ra4991 could have been detected using standard bioinformatics tools and data already available.

By demonstrating that a clear early warning signal was available in late December 2019 through routine analysis of existing databases but was apparently missed — or not acted upon — these results point to obvious areas for further investigation. Given the opacity surrounding these events and the profound stakes involved in timely pandemic detection, both for understanding the past and preparing for the future, a more thorough examination is clearly warranted. These findings also contribute to a better understanding of how real-time outbreak detection can and should be strengthened in future outbreaks.

References

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Appendix A: Detailed BLAST Parameters

Using the standard NCBI Nucleotide BLAST tool:

- Query: WH-01/2019 (December 28, 2019), using the cleaned FASTA file by Jesse Bloom
- Database: Nucleotide collection (nr/nt)
- Entrez Query: MH615898[Accession] OR ("2010/12/31":"2019/12/31"[PDAT])
- Program Selection: Optimize for highly similar sequences (Megablast)
- Sort Results by Per. Ident (Percent Identity)

This is an early preprint and has not been peer-reviewed. It is released in the spirit of open scientific inquiry to invite discussion, replication, and expert scrutiny. The central finding of this paper — that a strong, actionable match to Ra4991/RaTG13 linking SARS-CoV-2 to the Mojiang mine was technically detectable in December 2019 using only data and standard bioinformatics tools already present in the NIH GenBank system — represents a novel observation that, to the author's knowledge, has not been previously reported. The BLAST analysis serves as a replicable proof-of-concept demonstration of this method. I welcome constructive feedback, criticism, and further refinement from researchers with greater expertise in the field.

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